

MOISTURE ABSORPTION IN EPOXY / POLYETHERSULPHONE BLENDED RESINS

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ABSTRACT

The moisture absorption of an Epoxy / PES modified resin system, with thermoplastic contents from 0% to 40%w/w, was investigated. Tests were carried out at 297K, 313K and 353K and 100% relative humidity. Both one-dimensional and three-dimensional Fickian diffusion models were used to fit the data. The results suggest that, even with Shen and Springer's [1] edge correction factor, one dimensional analysis cannot adequately describe the absorption. Saturation levels, diffusivities and activation energies were determined for each blend. The addition of thermoplastic decreases saturation levels by 40%-50% and increases diffusivities by between 100%-200%; there is also a small decrease in activation energy. These trends are interpreted in terms of changes in chemical structure and morphology, between the blends.

INTRODUCTION

As the use of advanced material technology increases in the aerospace industry, so too do the demands for better performance. Recently the problem of moisture absorption into carbon fibre reinforced aircraft skins has been highlighted as an area of concern [2]. It has been known for many years that the uptake of moisture by a matrix system can result in serious reductions in mechanical properties [3], as well as leading to higher fuel consumption due to weight increase. In an attempt to combat this problem, a new blended resin system [4] has been produced. This system combines an epoxy thermosetting resin, with a polyethersulphone thermoplastic resin, resulting in a tough strong blended matrix. The aim of this work was to investigate this new system in terms of its absorption characteristics. Initially this was carried out in the neat resin form, with an aim to transferring this information to the final woven composite part.

Previous research [4] has revealed distinct morphological variations between each of these resin blends. The neat epoxy sample exhibits a single phase structure. As thermoplastic content is increased from 0 to 40% w/w so phase separation occurs, changing the structure from homogeneous to particulate, co-continuous and then finally phase-inverted. Dielectric examination has also revealed a reduction in polarity with increasing thermoplastic content. The following work sets out to determine the absorption characteristics of these new blends; and to show how their morphology and polarity variations can be used to explain observed trends in diffusion coefficients and saturation levels between the systems.

EXPERIMENTAL

A series of nine neat resin plaques was produced by ICI, in which the thermoplastic contents varied from 0 to 40% in 5% w/w steps. The blends were cast into open moulds in a preheated vacuum oven (418K), and were degassed under vacuum for 30 minutes. The samples were then cured at 458K for three hours in atmospheric air. Study has shown [5] that even slight variations in cure procedure can affect absorption characteristics, and so, a ramp up and ramp down temperature profile was used to emulate the cure cycle for the equivalent composite material.

Nine samples were cut from each plaque and were lightly abraded on all sides to remove any surface irregularities. The shape of the samples was restricted by the nature of the plaque geometries and the limited space available in the hot water tanks. The dimensions are as follows: a = 3.98mm (±0.39); b = 13.91mm (±0.62); c = 14.02mm (±0.64). These samples were placed in water (ie Relative Humidity, Rh = 100%) at 297K, 313K and 353K. Maximum exposure was achieved by supporting the samples on specially designed racks, ensuring point contact only.

Samples were periodically removed from the water and weighed on an analytical balance, to determine the percentage moisture uptake with time. Before each weighing, in order to eliminate surface moisture, three drying methods were used and compared. These were 'towel dried', 'air dried' and 'oven dried'. An average reading was determined for each sample from three weight measurements. The final moisture uptake values plotted for each system were, therefore, a result of nine readings, three readings from each of three specimens. Percentage moisture uptake values ranged from 0% to approximately 4.5% and standard deviations were of the order of 3E-02. During each weighing, samples were removed from the water for approximately 3 hours.

ANALYSIS

Eqn (1) shows the one-dimensional Fickian diffusion equation [1][6], for an infinite plate in a constant concentration environment. The equation assumes that moisture enters only through the two largest surfaces of the plate, and therefore takes no account of absorption through the edges. To correct for this, Shen and Springer [1] determined the 'edge effect' formula given in Eqn (2):

$$\frac{m_t}{m_m} = 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{\exp\left[-(2j+1)^2\pi^2\left(\frac{D_x t}{a^2}\right)\right]}{(2j+1)^2} \quad (1)$$

m_t = percentage moisture uptake at time t (normalised for original sample weight);
 m_m = maximum percentage moisture uptake (normalised for original sample weight);
 D_x = Diffusion coefficient in x direction (through sample thickness);
 a = sample thickness, j = positive whole integer, t = exposure time.

$$D' = D_x \left(1 + \frac{a}{b} + \frac{a}{c}\right)^{-2} \quad (2)$$

Where D' = Diffusion coefficient (representing the average diffusion coefficient for three-dimensional diffusion).

In order to validate this edge correction, the three-dimensional Fickian diffusion equation was also used. This was obtained by integrating the equation given by Carslaw and Jaeger [6], for diffusion as a function of time and position within the material. By integrating over the sample volume, and dividing by the volume, an equation for average moisture uptake as a function of time was obtained, as shown in Eqn (3). The equation allows for three different diffusion coefficients to be used, D_{xx} , D_{yy} and D_{zz} , in the case that the coefficient varies with direction. Here it is assumed that the material is isotropic and so $D_{xx}=D_{yy}=D_{zz}=D$.

$$\frac{m_t}{m_m} = 1 - \left(\frac{8}{\pi^2}\right)^3 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\exp\left(-D\pi^2\left(\frac{(2k-1)^2}{a^2} + \frac{(2l-1)^2}{b^2} + \frac{(2m-1)^2}{c^2}\right)t\right)}{((2k-1)(2l-1)(2m-1))^2} \quad (3)$$

k, l and m = positive whole integers; D = diffusion coefficient.

For the edge correction formula to be valid D must equal D'.

Diffusion is a thermally activated process and activation energies can be obtained from the absorption experiments. For this the Arrhenius equation for activation energy [7], as given in Eqn (4), is used.

$$D = D_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_d}{kT}\right) \quad (4)$$

Where; E_d = activation energy, D= diffusion coefficient, D_0 = frequency factor, k= Boltzmann's constant, T= temperature.

From Eqn (4) it can be seen that, by plotting $\ln(D)$ against $1/T$ and taking the gradients, values of the different activation energies for each blend can be determined. This plotting procedure is known as an Arrhenius plot. This can also be achieved by plotting $\ln(t_2-t_1)$ against $(1/T)$, where t_1 and t_2 are the times to reach certain points in the reaction. The latter method allows the determination of activation energies without recourse to a specific model [8].

RESULTS

Weight gain measurements were used to plot isothermal absorption graphs, as percentage moisture uptake against the square root of time. These plots were used to determine saturation levels, diffusion coefficients and activation energies. Fig. 1, shows the initial section of one such graph, (the 20% thermoplastic samples at 313K); the shape is typical of the shape of all other graphs obtained. The initial section of any absorption graph is expected to be linear, however in Fig. 1 it can be seen that all moisture uptake readings after $t=0$ are consistently too low. This is thought to be due to desorption of moisture back into the environment during the three hours it took for each weighing. A linear fit applied to these points yielded an intercept value of 0.072. This value was therefore added to all uptake values on the graph after $t=0$, to correct for desorption.

Figure 1. Correction applied to isotherms to account for desorption on weighing.

One dimensional and three dimensional Fickian diffusion equations (given in Eqns (1) and (2) respectively) were fitted to the full absorption isotherm. Fig. 2 shows the result of a typical fit. The same saturation level was used for both fits, i.e only the values of D_x and D were varied to obtain the best fit.

Figure 2. Absorption isotherm for 20% thermoplastic blend at 313K, with 1D and 3D fits.

It can be seen that the three dimensional curve gives a better fit to the experimental data. From these fits the following data was determined for the 20% thermoplastic blend at 313K: $m_m = 3.09\%$, $D_x = 1.8E-03\text{mm}^2\text{hr}^{-1}$, $D = 1.05E-03\text{mm}^2\text{hr}^{-1}$.

The errors associated with these fitting procedures are of the order of 10% for D and $\%m_m$. Hence, the value of diffusion coefficient predicted by the one-dimensional analysis is significantly higher than that predicted by three-dimensional analysis. This is because no account has been taken of edge effects. Multiplying by the correction factor given in Eqn (2), results in a value of D' of $0.74E-03\text{mm}^2\text{hr}^{-1}$. This value is closer to the three dimensional value, but it appears that the edge effect equation over estimates the effect of diffusion through the edges. As this is unsatisfactory it is necessary to continue analysis with the three-dimensional Fickian fit. As mentioned, tests were carried out at three temperatures; 297K, 313K and 353K. Unfortunately, the 353K tests were not able to be taken to full saturation due to equipment failure. In addition, the 297K tests are only just beyond the linear section of the absorption graph, despite being immersed for over 20 months. The 313K tests are therefore the most progressed experiments and thus the most capable of yielding accurate saturation level data.

It was therefore decided to use the 20% thermoplastic, 313K graph to extrapolate data from the other two test runs. This graph was fitted with the three dimensional diffusion equation as shown in Fig. 2, and values of diffusivity and saturation level were determined. In order to keep the fitting procedure consistent, all other graphs were 'fitted' to this base graph. In order to ensure variations in sample thickness were accounted for, all graphs were plotted against (Square root of time)/thickness. For each new graph, multiplication of the y-axis data and division of the x-axis data was carried out, until a 'fit' was obtained. The two values required for this numerical factoring were then recorded as M-Factor and D-Factor. Fig. 3 shows an example of this fitting procedure using the 0% thermoplastic blend at 297K.

Figure 3. Fit of 0% 297K data to base graph using M-factor and D-Factor.

The final values of $\%m_m$ and D are then obtained by using the formulae given below:
 $\%m_m = \%m_m \text{ (base graph)} / \text{M-Factor}$; $D = D \text{ (base graph)} \times (\text{D-Factor})^2$

The saturation levels determined using this method are shown in Fig. 4, along with a typical error bar for one of the readings.

Figure 4. Saturation levels as a function of thermoplastic content.

It can be seen from Fig. 4, that there is a consistent decrease in saturation level with the increase in thermoplastic content. At present it is difficult to determine if there is any change in saturation level with the change in temperature; a more accurate estimate will only be obtained when the tests are taken to completion.

Diffusion coefficients were also determined from the data fits; these are shown in Fig. 5. The errors in this case are equivalent to those for the saturation levels, and are of the order of 10%. Here again a trend is visible, this time it is for an increase in diffusivity with the increase in thermoplastic content.

Figure 5. Diffusion coefficients as a function of thermoplastic content and temperature.

Fig. 6 shows activation energies determined from the gradients of the Arrhenius plots, as described in the analysis section. These were determined using both diffusion coefficients (E_d), and the times for two stages in the reaction. The first time plot was for $\%m_t=1\%$ (E_{t1}) (ie the difference in time between 0% absorption and 1% absorption), and the second was for the difference in time between $\%m_t=1\%$ and $\%m_t=2\%$ (E_{t2-t1}).

Figure 6. Activation energies as a function of thermoplastic content.

The trend line shown is determined from the $\ln(t_2-t_1)$ versus $(1/T)$ plot, a typical error bar is also shown at 15% thermoplastic. The errors for the other two sets of data are of the same order. It can be seen that there is a general trend for decreasing activation energy with the increase in thermoplastic content.

DISCUSSION

The results given in the previous section have shown there to be at least two strong trends for changing absorption characteristics with the increase in thermoplastic content. For any significant variations in absorption characteristics between resin systems it is necessary to look to their physical and chemical structures for explanations. Previous work [4] on the blends has revealed distinct variations in their morphology, caused by phase separation of the constituents. The neat epoxy sample exhibits a single phase structure. At 5%-10% thermoplastic, phase separation occurs which leads to small occlusions of a thermoplastic rich phase in a continuum of epoxy rich phase. As thermoplastic levels reach 20%-25% the occlusions become ribbon-like, and at 30%-35% a co-continuous morphology is observed, where the two phases become continuous in three dimensions. The microstructure of the 40% system is as yet unknown. Dielectric examination has also revealed a consistent reduction in polarity with increasing thermoplastic content, implying that the neat epoxy contains more polar groups than the thermoplastic. It is likely that these two factors will be large contributors to the observed trends in absorption characteristics.

In terms of material characteristics which may influence diffusivity and maximum moisture uptake it is possible to identify; (i) bulk changes in free volume, (ii) bulk changes in polarity, and (iii) the presence of phase boundary regions.

Firstly, any significant increase in bulk free volume, brought about by morphological changes, would lead to an increase in diffusivity and in saturation level. Secondly, the cited decrease in polarity would lead to a reduction in the number of sites at which water is bound or released. This in turn might increase the diffusivity as the water molecules would require a lower activation energy to move between reactive sites. Indeed, results have shown there to be a general trend for a decrease in activation energy with the increase in thermoplastic content. The decrease in polarity could also reduce the maximum moisture uptake, as the water molecules could be held at fewer positions within the material. The third factor is the presence of phase boundary regions. This may also increase the diffusivity by acting as short circuits in the more contiguous morphology of the high thermoplastic blends.

Three possible factors have been shown to explain the observed trends in diffusion coefficient and saturation level. It is difficult at present to determine which of the three is the governing factor, but the simplest explanation would be for the bulk change in polarity to be the major contributor. S.E.M and T.E.M will now be used to further examine the blend microstructure to confirm any links between morphology variations and the observed phenomena. FTIR spectroscopy will be used to determine the occurrence of free and bound water within each blend. In conjunction with this, further investigation of the polarity of each system will be carried out, using simple dielectric experiments.

CONCLUSIONS

Tests have been carried out on a series of thermoplastic modified, thermoset resins, to determine absorption characteristics. It was determined that the one dimensional Fickian diffusion equation (even after correction for edge effects [1]), cannot adequately describe the observed absorption in small resin samples. Therefore, analysis was carried out with the three dimensional Fickian diffusion equation, which requires more computing time. This analysis has shown that the addition of a PES based resin, to an epoxy based system, results in a decrease in saturation level, an increase in diffusivity and a decrease in activation energy. Explanations for these results have been suggested in terms of the differences in morphology and polarity between the blends.

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